

From Code to Cobalt: Toward a Supply Chain–Aware Theory of AI Lifecycles

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Progress in Artificial Intelligence (AI) is associated with significant environmental costs due to the computational resources, energy, and materials these systems require. E.g., BLOOM –a 176-billion-parameter language model– emitted approximately 24.7 tonnes of CO₂-equivalent during final training and 50.5 tonnes when accounting for upstream and downstream processes, including equipment manufacturing and energy-based operational consumption. Most research in this area focuses on estimating emissions incurred during model training, often treating training as the primary source of AI’s environmental footprint. However, training constitutes only one, albeit significant, contributor to AI-related emissions and broader environmental impacts. While energy-intensive deployment, scaling, and infrastructure requirements have received increasing attention, systematic consideration of AI across its full lifecycle remains limited.

AI lifecycles are most often conceptualized as software-centric lifecycles of models or systems, overlooking the material, infrastructural, and hardware dependencies required to develop, deploy, and operate AI. In this sense, dominant AI lifecycles frame AI primarily as *software plus governance*, rather than as a materially grounded, supply chain-dependent sociotechnical system. Environmental sustainability thus exposes a fundamental blind spot in existing AI lifecycles – their treatment of AI as detached from its material and industrial conditions of production and operation, which resonates with the AI Supply Chain Impact Framework by the AI + Planetary Justice Alliance. Building on this insight, we conceptualize AI as *a sociotechnical system characterized by tight complementarity between software, hardware, infrastructure, and organizational practices*. Going beyond Green AI as an analytical lens, we propose a **supply chain–aware AI lifecycle** that embeds established AI system lifecycles, such as those articulated by the OECD, NIST, and ISO, within a broader material and infrastructural value chain.

In contrast to traditional AI lifecycles that begin with system design, the proposed lifecycle starts upstream with raw material extraction, encompassing the mining and processing of critical minerals required for AI hardware. At the downstream end, it explicitly includes hardware end-of-life and disposal, addressing what happens to servers, GPUs, and other computing equipment once they are decommissioned or rendered obsolete – dimensions typically absent from conventional AI lifecycles. Rather than replacing existing AI lifecycles, our approach situates them as a core subsystem within a wider value chain capturing upstream and downstream environmental impacts.

Specifically, the proposed AI lifecycle spans upstream *hardware production – raw material extraction, materials and equipment manufacturing*, followed by the AI system lifecycle comprising *system planning and design, data collection and processing, model development and adaptation, testing and validation, deployment, operation, monitoring and scaling, and system modification, retraining, or retirement*, and concludes with downstream hardware *end-of-life and disposal*. While the proposed lifecycle could be represented linearly, consistent with Life-Cycle Assessment approaches, we conceptualize it instead as a supply chain within which the AI system operates as an iterative cycle. This reflects empirical realities in which monitoring triggers retraining, model updates alter compute requirements, and deployment decisions feed back into hardware demand. Beyond Green AI, the proposed lifecycle provides a generalizable lens for analyzing labour and invisible work, political-economic dependencies, and organizational decision-making in AI governance.

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